

ATRIUM Researchers Survey

This survey has been developed as part of Task 7.1 within the [ATRIUM Project](#), funded by the European Commission under grant agreement n°101132163. The aim is to assess if researchers from Social Sciences, Humanities, and Arts have the skills required for the active use of research services and tools, namely the ones available in the [ATRIUM Catalogue](#). The other main goal is to provide recommendations for training materials to be considered for the ATRIUM Curriculum.

Here is the [information sheet](#) about how the data gathered in this survey will be processed. Please, read it carefully.

If you have any questions, please contact Carol Delmazo, Task 7.1 leader: carol.delmazo@operas-eu.org.

* Indicates required question

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Section 1: Demographics and Background

The goal of this section is to understand your context: who do you work for and from where, the scientific domain, and the work languages.

1. 1.1. Affiliation *

2. **1.2. In which country are you based? ***

 Dropdown

Mark only one oval.

- Afghanistan
- Albania
- Algeria
- Andorra
- Angola
- Antigua and Barbuda
- Argentina
- Armenia
- Australia
- Austria
- Azerbaijan
- Bahamas
- Bahrain
- Bangladesh
- Barbados
- Belarus
- Belgium
- Belize
- Benin
- Bhutan
- Bolivia
- Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Botswana
- Brazil
- Brunei
- Bulgaria
- Burkina Faso
- Burundi
- Cabo Verde
- Cambodia

- Cameroon
- Canada
- Central African Republic
- Chad
- Chile
- China
- Colombia
- Comoros
- Congo, Democratic Republic of the
- Congo, Republic of the
- Costa Rica
- Côte d'Ivoire
- Croatia
- Cuba
- Cyprus
- Czech Republic
- Denmark
- Djibouti
- Dominica
- Dominican Republic
- East Timor (Timor-Leste)
- Ecuador
- Egypt
- El Salvador
- Equatorial Guinea
- Eritrea
- Estonia
- Eswatini
- Ethiopia
- Fiji
- Finland
- France
- Gabon

- Gambia
- Georgia
- Germany
- Ghana
- Greece
- Grenada
- Guatemala
- Guinea
- Guinea-Bissau
- Guyana
- Haiti
- Honduras
- Hungary
- Iceland
- India
- Indonesia
- Iran
- Iraq
- Ireland
- Israel
- Italy
- Jamaica
- Japan
- Jordan
- Kazakhstan
- Kenya
- Kiribati
- Korea, North
- Korea, South
- Kosovo
- Kuwait
- Kyrgyzstan
- Laos

- Latvia
- Lebanon
- Lesotho
- Liberia
- Libya
- Liechtenstein
- Lithuania
- Luxembourg
- Madagascar
- Malawi
- Malaysia
- Maldives
- Mali
- Malta
- Marshall Islands
- Mauritania
- Mauritius
- Mexico
- Micronesia, Federated States of
- Moldova
- Monaco
- Mongolia
- Montenegro
- Morocco
- Mozambique
- Myanmar (Burma)
- Namibia
- Nauru
- Nepal
- Netherlands
- New Zealand
- Nicaragua
- Niger

- Nigeria
- North Macedonia
- Norway
- Oman
- Pakistan
- Palau
- Panama
- Papua New Guinea
- Paraguay
- Peru
- Philippines
- Poland
- Portugal
- Qatar
- Romania
- Russia
- Rwanda
- Saint Kitts and Nevis
- Saint Lucia
- Saint Vincent and the Grenadines
- Samoa
- San Marino
- Sao Tome and Principe
- Saudi Arabia
- Senegal
- Serbia
- Seychelles
- Sierra Leone
- Singapore
- Slovakia
- Slovenia
- Solomon Islands
- Somalia

- South Africa
- Spain
- Sri Lanka
- Sudan
- Sudan, South
- Suriname
- Sweden
- Switzerland
- Syria
- Taiwan
- Tajikistan
- Tanzania
- Thailand
- Togo
- Tonga
- Trinidad and Tobago
- Tunisia
- Turkey
- Turkmenistan
- Tuvalu
- Uganda
- Ukraine
- United Arab Emirates
- United Kingdom
- United States
- Uruguay
- Uzbekistan
- Vanuatu
- Vatican City
- Venezuela
- Vietnam
- Yemen
- Zambia

Zimbabwe

3. **1.3. What is/are your working language(s)? ***

Check all that apply.

- Czech
- Dutch
- English
- French
- German
- Greek
- Italian
- Polish
- Portuguese
- Spanish
- Other: _____

4. **1.4. What is your scientific domain? ***

If you have doubts, please check out points 5 and 6 of the [Revised Field of Science and Technology](#) (FOS) from the OECD.

Check all that apply.

- Arts
- Humanities
- Social Sciences
- Other

5. **1.5. Are you doing research in Archaeology? ***

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

6. **1.6. Which community group do you identify with? ***

Mark only one oval.

- Masters student
- PhD student
- Early-career researcher (up to 7 years working in the field)
- Mid-career researcher (7-12 years working in the field)
- Senior researcher (12+ years working in the field)
- Other

Section 2: Your data

This section consists of a few questions regarding your research activities and the type of data you work with.

7. **2.1. What does your research activity consist of? ***

Check all that apply.

- Project management
- Data modelling
- Cataloguing
- Data collection (e.g. from archives, repositories)
- Data cleansing/preparation (e.g. removal of unnecessary data for the research topic, filtering)
- Information extraction (e.g. part-of-speech tagging, layout annotation, named entity recognition, coreference resolution, relationship extraction, speech recognition)
- Data processing (e.g. transcriptions, Automatic Text Recognition)
- Data analysis
- Data visualisation
- Data publication
- Data preservation/archiving
- Other

8. **2.2. What types of data are you working with? ***

Check all that apply.

- Textual
- Tabular
- Images
- Geospatial
- Audio
- Video
- 3D models
- Graph data
- Other

9. **2.3.1. Are you working with born-digital data? ***

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (born-digital only) *Skip to question 11*
- No *Skip to question 10*
- Both *Skip to question 10*

10. **2.3.2. If your data are not born-digital, have they been digitised? ***

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

Section 3: Knowledge of Open Science and FAIR

Open Science is at the centre of the [European research policy](#). Knowledge of Open Science and FAIR data principles is an important background for the use of the services and tools provided by ATRIUM.

11. **3.1. How familiar are you with the principles and practices of Open Science? ***

Mark only one oval.

- Not familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Familiar

12. **3.2. To what extent do you apply Open Science practices in your research? ***

Mark only one oval.

- I have no interest in applying them.
- I am exploring ways to apply them in my research, or I apply them to some extent (e.g. publishing articles in Open Access, making my data as open as possible)
- I apply them extensively in my research (e.g. doing pre-registration, I publish methods)

13. **3.3. How familiar are you with the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) data principles? ***

Mark only one oval.

- Not familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Familiar

14. **3.4. To what extent do you apply the FAIR data principles in your research? ***

Mark only one oval.

- I have no interest in applying them.
- I am exploring ways to apply them in my research, or I apply them to some extent (e.g. sharing my data in a public repository, assigning DOIs to datasets, providing basic metadata, using Creative Commons licenses)
- I apply them extensively in my research (e.g. assessing my data for FAIRness before publication, creating detailed metadata using domain-specific standards, providing supporting documentation, and actively engaging with the research community to promote FAIR practices)

Section 4: Skills for the use of research services and tools

The aim of this section is to assess skills related to the use of research services and tools. Some require very specific ones, while some are easier to use. The ATRIUM project promotes a comprehensive set of services and tools designed to support all the stages in the enabled data-driven research: the [ATRIUM Catalogue](#).

15. **4.1. What digital tools or services do you use in your research activities?** (e.g. spreadsheets, tools/services for transcription, data visualisation, translation, project management, data mapping, collaboration, etc.) **Please, name the specific tools or services used.**

16. **4.2.1. How familiar are you with standards, controlled vocabularies, and thesauri?** (e.g. TEI, Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM, Getty AAT, Getty TGN, SKOS) *

Mark only one oval.

- Not familiar: I've never heard about them. *Skip to question 18*
- Somewhat familiar: I am aware of them, but I do not always use them.
Skip to question 17
- Familiar: I understand their importance and use them steadily.
Skip to question 17

17. **4.2.2. Which standards, controlled vocabularies, and thesauri do you usually apply in your research?** *
-

Section 4: Skills for the use of research services and tools

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18. **4.3. What is your experience with Automatic Text Recognition (ATR) technologies?** (e.g. Optical Character Recognition [OCR], Handwritten Text Recognition [HTR]) *

Mark only one oval.

- I don't know what ATR consists of, or I can only transcribe documents manually
- I know how to apply an existing model to my documents, and correct the automatic transcription if I am working with a graphical user interface like eScriptorium or Transkribus
- I know how to fine-tune a model or create one from scratch, and am aware of the importance and role of ground truth data.

19. **4.4. Have you ever used a command-line interface? ***

Mark only one oval.

- I don't know what a command-line interface is, or I have never used it.
- I can perform basic commands (e.g. creating and navigating within directories).
- I can use a command-line interface to open, modify, move, and delete files, install software, and perform automated tasks.

20. **4.5.1. What is your experience with coding or programming? ***

Mark only one oval.

- I have no experience, or I have a basic understanding of how algorithms work without knowing any programming language. *Skip to question 22*
- I understand the syntax, and can write simple scripts (e.g. automating minor tasks). *Skip to question 21*
- I am comfortable with the core features of the language (complex data structures, functions), work with libraries and frameworks, and am able to debug code. *Skip to question 21*

21. **4.5.2. What programming language(s) do you work with? ***

Check all that apply.

- JavaScript
- Python
- R
- Other: _____

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22. **4.6. What is your experience with encoding languages?** (e.g. XML, HTML) *

Mark only one oval.

- I have never encoded a document and don't know how I should do it.
- I understand the hierarchical tree-like architecture of such languages, and know basic syntactic encoding rules.
- I am comfortable with adapting my encoding to a standard (e.g. TEI) to make my encoding both well-formed and valid.

23. **4.7. What is your experience with Docker or other container management tools/platforms?** (e.g. Kubernetes) *

Mark only one oval.

- I don't know what a container management tool/platform is, or I have never used one.
- I use DockerHub and can manage a Docker container (e.g. Docker engine).
- I know how to manage code, data, and images (repository) with Docker in the command-line interface.

24. **4.8. What is your experience with GitHub/GitLab?** *

Mark only one oval.

- I have never heard of (one of) them, or I have never used them, except maybe by clicking on a link provided by a colleague.
- I have browsed or downloaded from (one of) them, and/or I have opened or managed tickets/issues for a project I am collaborating with.
- I use (one of) them to manage my code and data, and possibly collaborate with external projects (e.g. pull requests, open source collaboration). I can make the difference between Git and GitHub/GitLab.

25. **4.9. What is your experience with Web APIs (Application Programming Interfaces)?** *

Mark only one oval.

- I have never heard of them, or I have never used them.
- I have a basic understanding of APIs and can use them to access or retrieve data from other platforms.
- I am comfortable using APIs to connect different systems, retrieve and send data, and understand how to make requests (e.g. GET, POST) to interact with online services.

Section 5: Training needs

This section explores the needs of researchers regarding online learning and training resources. The questions are intended to gather insights into the types of learning content you seek, your preferred learning formats, and any challenges you might face.

26. **5.1. Have you used open educational learning resources from any online (infrastructure) platform? Please check all that apply.** *

If you use other platforms, please check "Other" and name them.

Check all that apply.

- ARIADNEplus Training Hub
- DARIAH Campus
- CLARIN Learning Hub
- OPERAS training materials
- None
- Other: _____

27. **5.2. What skills or knowledge would you like to gain through online learning resources?** (e.g. Open Science, FAIR data principles, workflows, Automatic Text Recognition, data visualisation, data analysis, data publication, etc.) *

28. **5.3. Which format(s) of training materials do you find more effective? ***

Check all that apply.

- Written manuals, guidelines
- Video tutorials with exercises (self-paced)
- Live interactive webinars, workshops
- Blended learning (combination of self-paced and live sessions)
- Other: _____

29. **5.4. Do you find quizzes useful to self-assess your knowledge as part of your learning content? ***

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Indifferent

30. **5.5. What challenges do you face when using online learning resources? (e.g. difficulty finding resources, quality/credibility of resources, stopping and restarting online courses, lack of certification, etc.) ***

31. **5.6. Is there something else you would like to share about your online learning experience and your needs for training resources?**

Section 6: Data processing and future contacts

Here is the [information sheet](#) about how the data gathered in this survey will be processed. Please, read it carefully.

32. **Data processing** *

Check all that apply.

By checking this, I confirm that I read the information on how my data will be processed within the ATRIUM project and I agree with that.

33. **We are not collecting emails automatically.** Please share your email if you are open to follow-up questions or participating in a focus group or interview:

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